

ESTABLISHING A SILVOPASTORAL CATTLE SYSTEM IN IRELAND

COMBINING CATTLE WITH FORESTRY

1. Cattle grazing in highly stocked young oak woodland 2. Dairy cows grazing amongst individually protected trees 3. Grass sward cut for fodder (silage) harvest 4. Mechanised fodder harvest in a silvopastoral system

WHAT AND WHY

Why cattle and forestry can be mutually beneficial

High production systems prioritize high-protein grasses but often lack resilience, shelter, shade, and dietary diversity for livestock. Silvopasture enhances grassland management by adding complexity and resilience.

Cattle can play a crucial role in maintaining woodland pastures. Their grazing and trampling promote the growth of pasture plants while limiting the spread of woody undergrowth. Although in Ireland most domesticated cattle spend their lives in open, enclosed pastures, they naturally seek the shade and shelter of trees during adverse weather. In wooded areas, cattle demonstrate behavioural changes, including reduced flight zones and increased social interactions.

Moreover, when given access to diverse vegetation, cattle instinctively consume a variety of plants, such as grasses, leaves from hedges, shrubs, and trees. Historically, wild cattle inhabited environments that included a mix of open pastures, woodland pastures, and dense forests, showcasing their adaptability to different landscapes.

Silvopasture, as sustainable land management system, mimics these natural woodland pastures by integrating trees and pastures. This approach allows cattle to exhibit their natural behaviours while fostering ecological balance.

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

How to establish a silvopastoral system

Establishing silvopasture requires careful planning, tree protection, and maintenance. One approach is to fence small to medium areas for tree planting, keeping livestock out until trees are sturdy enough to withstand grazing pressure. More mature trees can withstand short-duration grazing, especially in autumn when livestock are less likely to damage bark. Alternatively individual tree shelters can be employed, but restrictions on cattle size will exist until the trees are firmly established. Another approach is to fence off small areas of trees, to allow for immediate grazing within the remaining pasture. Over time, the fences can be removed for open access.

Trees enhance soil structure, water infiltration, and grazing seasons, but proper livestock management is vital. Rotational grazing prevents overuse, bark damage, and soil compaction around roots, protecting both trees and pastures.

Keywords: Ireland, Silvopasture, Cattle, Shelter, Browse, Productivity

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ADVANTAGES

Soil Restoration

Fast-growing trees like alder, birch, and willow improve poor soils by reducing compaction, enhancing structure, and fostering beneficial fungi that can help suppress rushes. Their roots can increase water infiltration by up to 60% and improve soil organic carbon by approximately 20%. Additionally, well-structured soils filter and store water, reducing runoff by as much as 30%, which helps protect watercourses.

Shelter and Shade

Trees create a microclimate that is 2–4°C cooler in summer and 1–3°C warmer in winter, extending the grazing season. As the trees develop, their shade reduces heat stress, which can lead to a 10–20% loss in milk or meat production if unaddressed. Cattle may use up to 40% of feed energy just to regulate body temperature during extreme heat, impacting productivity and fertility. Silvopastoral shade can significantly mitigate these negative effects.

Browse

Browse—leaves and twigs from woody plants—provides nutrients that may be lacking in pastures. *Salix* (willow) and *Quercus* (oak) leaves, for example, possess condensed tannins that reduce parasitic loads by up to 30%. Willow also contains salicylic acid, a natural anti-inflammatory, and cobalt, which supports overall health. Access to browse can boost feed diversity, leading to healthier livestock and improved resilience.

Grass fodder source

If the trees have individual shelters at establishment, it is recommended that only young cattle be grazed during the spring and summer months for the first six to eight years, depending on tree growth. Thereafter, when tree shelters are replaced with mesh, larger animals may be introduced. Fodder (silage and hay) production is also possible between widely spaced rows of trees. Appropriate machinery must be used when cutting fodder so that the trees are not inadvertently damaged.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- Trees can reduce heat stress by 2–4°C in summer and warm by 1–3°C in winter, extending grazing and avoiding 10–20% milk or meat losses.
- Willow provides anti-inflammatories and cobalt, while oak tannins can lower parasite loads by up to 30%, boosting cattle health.
- Alder, birch, and willow can improve infiltration by 60%, raise soil carbon by 20%, and cut runoff by 30%, protecting watercourses.

Tree planting to reduce run-off from grazing land

Further Information:

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